

Some Indenoquinoline Derivatives.

BY GURCHARAN SINGH AND JNANENDRA NATH RAY.

At the present time the lower homologue of benzene (C_5H_5) or its derivatives have not been prepared. Armit and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 827) came to the conclusion that this type of bodies can be derived from the decomposition of a quaternary hydroxide containing the group (I) or an analogous structure.

Types analogous to (I) can be readily prepared from the methoxyhydroxides derived from indenoquinolines. One of these has already received the attention of Armit and Robinson (*loc. cit.*) and accordingly these were chosen for examination in the first place. Armit and Robinson condensed aminopiperonal and α -hydrindone in cold alcoholic solution in presence of potassium hydroxide but they got an unexpected result. The product was the unsaturated ketone (II) which, however, was changed into the quinoline (III) on treatment with acetic acid.

The obvious difficulty of extending this reaction led to its abandonment, and they looked for in other directions for the realisation of the structure (CH)₅ in association with other ring-systems. In the present paper, we found reasons, which would be stated later on, why it is so very difficult to deal with compounds of this character. Moreover, aminoaldehydes are rather tedious and difficult to prepare. It seemed to us that if a suitable way is found to effect a condensation between an *o*-nitroaldehyde and hydrindones the products are more likely to lead to the desired quinolines on reduction. But the obvious difficulty is that the only method employed hitherto for effecting a condensation between a nitroaldehyde and a reactive methylene group is by the employment of alkali or ethoxides of alkali metals. But the very nature of the condensing agent restricts its applicability and therefore as a preliminary to the main investigation we turned our attention to the finding out of a suitable means of bringing about these condensations. Our object was to try the reactions between a compound containing -CO·CH₂-group and various *o*-nitroaldehydes. Alkali was first chosen as a condensing agent. Since the hydrindones are difficult to prepare, therefore, we decided in the first place to employ desoxybenzoin, Ph·CO·CH₂·Ph (a substance easily available and having the same reactive grouping) as a trial substance.

The condensation of desoxybenzoin with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde in presence of alkali as a condensing agent gave two products having melting points 110° and 210°, respectively. To the first we could not assign any structure, but the second compound (IV) is formed according to the following equation :

Although the isolation of two products, one of uncertain constitution, indicated that alkali is hardly a suitable reagent yet we attempted to use the alkali in the condensation of hydrindone and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, but this failed, and after many fruitless trials with different agents it was ultimately found that this condensation takes place in presence of acetic anhydride.

o-Hydrindone, methylenedioxyhydrindone and dimethoxyhydrindone were thus condensed with *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde, nitropiperonal

and nitroveratric aldehyde to give the corresponding *o*-nitro- $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketones.

The reduction of the nitroarylidenehydrindones presented considerable difficulty. This at first seemed to be of a puzzling character, seeing that Armit and Robinson had already, although not satisfactorily, reduced (V) to (III).

We employed sodium sulphide as a most likely reducing agent but we were unfortunately not able to isolate any pure product. This we later found out to be due to the fact that in alkaline medium (as well as in acid medium) the quinolines formed immediately underwent oxidation. We are inclined to think that the ring 3 in (III) is the one which is oxidised to the form,

along with probably many other associated products and that is why the isolation of these derivatives of *cyclopentamethine* is so very difficult. Next we turned our attention to the employment of zinc dust and acetic acid for these reductions, but here an unexpected difficulty presented itself. With the progress of the reduction brilliant fluorescence appeared in the solution, but from the reaction product nothing crystalline could be isolated. This we did not understand for a while but subsequently it was found that if air was rigorously excluded from the reaction vessel and particular care was taken to free the zinc dust from zinc oxide, these fluorescence ceased to appear. The desired indenoquinolines could then be isolated, if the whole of the operation be conducted in an atmosphere of hydrogen and to the total exclusion of air. This appearance of fluorescence obviously was due to the rapid oxidation of the ring 3 of (III) to the pentamethine derivative by air.

Our objective was to isolate these pentamethine derivatives, therefore we allowed, for a time, the air to play the rôle of an oxidising agent with the hope that it would be possible to isolate our desired pentamethines.

The pentamethines are more likely to be fluorescent than indenoquinolines. This is why with the introduction of air intense fluorescence appears, but the action probably does not stop at this stage and proceeds further and that is why the isolation of the pentamethine in a state of purity, is not possible. After many attempts to isolate such oxidation product, we gave up the project and decided first to isolate the indenoquinoline and therefore carried on the reduction to the total exclusion of air, and then proceed on to the oxidation of these to the pentamethine derivatives, as it was thought by starting from the pure substances we were more likely to isolate the pentamethine derivatives. Therefore in the experimental part, we describe the isolation of these indenoquinolines and reserve, for the time being, the conversion of these indenoquinolines to the pentamethines.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The following modification worked better in the preparation of 6-nitroveratric aldehyde (*cf.* Pschorr and Sumuleanu, *Ber.*, 1899, **32**, 3412) and nitropiperonal.

Veratric aldehyde (15 g.) was gradually introduced into nitric acid (30 g., *d* 1.42) kept at 5-10°, with stirring. The product was diluted with ice-water and the yellow crystals collected, washed with ice-water and recrystallised from alcohol; m.p. 132-33°; yield 70 per cent.

Piperonal (15 g.) dissolved in 8 c.c. of acetic acid was gradually added to nitric acid (16 c.c., *d* 1.5) kept below 6°. A little more of acetic acid was found to hinder the nitration. When all of the piperonal was added, the product was allowed to remain at the same temperature for about fifteen minutes, then poured on to water, the yellow crystals collected and recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. 95°.

Condensation of Desoxybenzoin with o-Nitrobenzaldehyde: Formation of (IV).—Desoxybenzoin (19.6 g.) and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (15.1 g. dissolved in 100 c.c. of alcohol) were mixed with 1 c.c. (50 per cent.) potassium hydroxide solution. It was then refluxed on the water-bath for an hour, cooled and poured on to water, and the solid product collected. It consists of two substances one of which is

readily soluble in hot alcohol and the other insoluble. The soluble portion crystallises in long, yellow needles melting at 110°. (Found: N, 6.1 per cent. M.W. 258). As these results do not agree with that of any of the expected compounds, we could not assign any structure to it.

The insoluble portion was dried and crystallised from benzene. This compound melts at 210° and the crystals are bright yellow in colour. (Found: N, 4.5. $C_{21}H_{15}O_3N$ requires N, 4.3 per cent.). Attempts to reduce this product failed.

*Condensation of α -Hydrindone with *o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde: Formation of 2'-Nitrobenzylidene- α -hydrindone.*—Hydrindone (13.2 g.), *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde (15.1 g.) and acetic anhydride (40 c.c.) were heated for two hours under reflux. The product solidified in contact with water which was collected and best crystallised from glacial acetic acid in pale needles, m.p. 167°. (Found: N, 5.4. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 5.3 per cent.). The compound is sparingly soluble in hot alcohol but is readily soluble in hot acetic acid.

Reduction of the above Compound: Formation of Indenoquinoline.—The nitrobenzylidenehydrindone was heated with zinc dust and acetic acid for an hour and then filtered while hot. On addition of water the quinoline separated out as a chalky precipitate, which was collected and dried. This product was very difficult to crystallise. The compound was dissolved in alcohol, to which a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid were added. This on dilution with a little water deposited pale yellow crystals, m.p. 170-75°. The hydrochloride is sparingly soluble in aqueous alcohol. (Found: N, 5.8. $C_{16}H_{11}N.HCl$ requires N, 5.52 per cent.).

In this case no fluorescence appears, and probably the reduced product here is not so easily oxidisable by air.

Condensation of α -Hydrindone with 6-Nitropiperonal: Formation of 6'-Nitro-3':4'-methyleneedioxybenzylidenehydrindone.—Hydrindone (13.2 g.), 6-nitropiperonal (19.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (40 c.c.) were condensed as before. The product was poured on to water; on cooling, the yellow crystals were collected, and recrystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow prisms, m.p. 178°; yield, 6 g. (Found: C, 65.8; H, 3.7; N, 4.7. $C_{17}H_{11}O_5N$ requires C, 66.0; H, 3.5; N, 4.5 per cent.). The substance is sparingly soluble in hot alcohol but is quite soluble in glacial acetic acid. This compound has been prepared before by Armit and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 125, 827) who give m.p. 182°.

*Reduction of Nitropiperonylidenehydrindone: Formation of 6': 7'-Methylenedioxy-2: 8-indeno-1: 2-quinoline Hydrochloride (III).—*This compound was obtained by heating 6-nitropiperonylidenehydrindone with zinc dust and acetic acid. The solution first developed an orange-red colour which with the progress of the reaction changed to light orange. Nitropiperonylidenehydrindone is first reduced to the amino-compound which further is quickly converted into the quinoline derivative. This experiment presented considerable difficulty as it had to be performed in complete absence of air and the whole operation done in the presence of hydrogen.

Zinc dust and acetic acid were first gently boiled for a few minutes to destroy any zinc oxide present in the zinc, and also to chase all the air from the reaction vessel. Then the nitro-compound was gradually added with occasional shaking and the heating continued till the reduction was complete. Near the end of the reaction the colour of the solution became lighter (about $1\frac{1}{2}$ hour). Then the mixture was quickly filtered in an atmosphere of hydrogen into a flask containing ice, and kept cold in a freezing bath, through which hydrogen was constantly passing. The filtrate was completely neutralised with a cold solution of strong sodium hydroxide kept in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The quinoline which separated out was extracted by ether in an atmosphere of hydrogen, the ethereal solution filtered into a distillation flask from which air has been expelled by saturating it with ether vapour. The dried ethereal solution was distilled, the oily residue dissolved in alcohol and the hydrochloride formed by adding concentrated hydrochloric acid which deposited brick-red crystals on dilution with a little water. The hydrochlorides of this series are curiously soluble in alcohol but almost insoluble in aqueous alcohol. The compound shrinks at 194° and melts with decomposition at 197° . (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{17}H_{11}O_2N$. HCl requires N, 4.7 per cent.).

Condensation of α -Hydrindone with Nitroveratric Aldehyde: Formation of 6'-Nitro-3': 4'-dimethoxybenzylidene- α -hydrindone.— α -Hydrindone (13.2 g.), nitroveratric aldehyde (21.1 g.) and acetic anhydride (40 c.c.) were condensed as before. On cooling the product was poured on to water and the yellow crystals separating out collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. (Found: N, 4.9. $C_{18}H_{15}O_5N$ requires N, 4.3 per cent.). This compound melts at 210° and crystallises in yellow needles.

Condensation of Methyleneedioxyhydrindone and o-Nitrobenzaldehyde: Formation of 6'-Nitrobenzylidene-3:4-methyleneedioxyhydrindone.—3:4-Methyleneedioxyhydrindone (17.6 g.), o-nitrobenzaldehyde (15.1 g.) and acetic anhydride (40 c.c.) were heated under reflux for two hours. On cooling the product was poured on to water and allowed to remain for some time. The solid which separated out was collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. (Found: N, 4.6. $C_{17}H_{11}O_5N$ requires N, 4.5 per cent.); yield, 8 g. The compound melts at 212° and crystallises in yellow needles.

Reduction of the above Compound: Formation of Methyleneedioxyindenoquinoline.—6'-Nitrobenzylidene-3:4-methyleneedioxyhydrindone, zinc dust and acetic acid were heated for an hour. The solution first showed a deep uranium-blue fluorescence which practically disappeared with the progress of the reaction. The solution was then quickly filtered, neutralised with caustic soda; the precipitate of the free base collected, dried and crystallised from a mixture of benzene and petroleum ether. (Found: N, 5.6. $C_{17}H_{11}O_2N$ requires N, 5.4 per cent.). The compound shrinks at 195° and melts at 202°.

Condensation of Methyleneedioxyhydrindone with Nitropiperonal: Formation of 6'-Nitro-3':4'-methyleneedioxybenzylidene-3:4-methyleneedioxyhydrindone.—3:4-Methyleneedioxyhydrindone (17.6 g.), nitropiperonal (19.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (40 c.c.) were condensed as before. The product on cooling was poured on to water, the solid collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. (Found: N, 4.1. $C_{18}H_{11}O_7N$ requires N, 4.0 per cent.). The compound crystallises in deep yellow needles melting at 232°; yield, 12 g.

Reduction of the above Compound: Formation of Dimethylene-dioxyindenoquinoline.—6'-Nitropiperonylidene-3:4-methyleneedioxyhydrindone was added to acetic acid and zinc dust, which had already been boiling for some time. After 1½ hour the solution was filtered into a flask containing ice and kept cool from outside, and through which hydrogen was constantly passing. The filtrate was then completely neutralised with a cold solution of strong sodium hydroxide kept in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The quinoline which separated out was extracted with ether in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The ethereal solution on distillation furnished the quinoline as a pale white crystalline mass, m.p. 289°. (Found: N, 4.7. $C_{18}H_{11}O_4N$ requires N, 4.6 per cent.).

Condensation of Methylenedioxyhydrindone and Nitroveratric Aldshyde: Formation of 6'-Nitro-3':4'-dimethoxybenzylidene-3:4-methylenedioxyhydrindone.—3:4-Methylenedioxyhydrindone (17.6 g.), nitroveratric aldshyde (21.1 g.) and acetic anhydride (40 c.c.) were condensed as before. On cooling, the product was poured on to water, the yellow needles collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid; m.p. 250°. (Found: N, 3.9. $C_{19}H_{15}O_7N$ requires N, 3.8 per cent.).

Reduction of the above Compound: Formation of Dimethoxy-methylenedioxyindenoquinoline.—6'-Nitro-3':4'-dimethoxybenzylidene-3:4-methylenedioxyhydrindone was added to a mixture of zinc dust and acetic acid which had been kept boiling. The solution develops a deep orange colour in the beginning which changes to pale yellow with the progress of the reaction. After 1½ hour the solution was quickly filtered in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The filtrate was then neutralised with an ice-cold solution of strong caustic soda in an atmosphere of hydrogen. The quinoline which separated out was extracted with ether, the ether distilled off, care being taken to exclude air. The oily mass left behind was dissolved in alcohol, to which concentrated hydrochloric acid was added, and the hydrochloride crystallised out in yellow needles on addition of water. The compound shrinks at 255° and melts with decomposition at 257°. (Found: N, 4.1. $C_{19}H_{15}O_4N$, HCl requires N, 3.9 per cent.).

Condensation of 3:4-Dimethoxyhydrindone with o-Nitrobenzaldehyde: Formation of 6'-Nitrobenzylidene-3:4-dimethoxyhydrindone.—3:4-Dimethoxyhydrindone (19.2 g.), o-nitrobenzaldehyde (15.1 g.) and acetic anhydride (40 c.c.) were condensed as before. The product was crystallised from glacial acetic acid in lemon yellow needles, m.p. 188°; yield, 12 g. (Found: N, 4.5. $C_{19}H_{15}O_5N$ requires N, 4.3 per cent.).

Reduction of the above Compound: Formation of Dimethoxyindenoquinoline Hydrochloride.—The nitrobenzylidenedimethoxyhydrindone was reduced as before. The solution first showed orange-yellow colour which almost disappeared near the end of the reaction. After heating for 1½ hour the solution was filtered quickly in an atmosphere of hydrogen and the filtrate neutralized with a strong solution of caustic soda. The quinoline was extracted with ether; the ethereal solution showed a very pale bluish-yellow fluorescence. The free base left behind as an oily mass was converted into its hydrochloride by taking it an alcohol, adding concentrated hydro-

chloric acid and crystallising by addition of water. The hydrochloride came out in pale yellow crystals, which shrink at 231° and melt with decomposition at 232°. (Found: Cl, 10.6; N, 4.67. $C_{18}H_{15}O_2N$, HCl requires Cl, 11.8; N, 4.47 per cent.).

Condensation of 3:4-Dimethoxyhydrindone with Nitropiperonal: Formation of 6'-Nitro-3':4'-methylenedioxybenzylidene-3:4-dimethoxyhydrindone.—3:4-Dimethoxyhydrindone (19.2 g.), nitropiperonal (19.5 g.) and acetic anhydride (40 c.c.) were condensed as before, and the product crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow needles; m.p. 232°. (Found: N, 4.0. $C_{16}H_{15}O_7N$ requires N, 3.8 per cent.).

Reduction of the above Compound: Formation of Methylenedioxydimethoxyindenoquinoline.—Nitropiperonylidenedimethoxyhydrindone was reduced as before. The solution first showed a deep red colour which became lighter with the progress of the reaction. After the heating had been continued for 1½ hour the solution was treated as in the other cases. The quinoline obtained as an oily mass was converted into its hydrochloride, which crystallised in yellow crystals on dilution with water, m.p. 270° with decomp. (Found: N, 3.9. $C_{16}H_{15}O_4N$, HCl requires N, 3.9 per cent.).

Condensation of Dimethoxyhydrindone with Nitroveratric Aldehyde: Formation of 6'-Nitro-3':4'-dimethoxybenzylidene-3:4-dimethoxyhydrindone.—3:4-Dimethoxyhydrindone (19.2 g.), nitroveratric aldehyde (21.1 g.) and acetic anhydride (40 c.c.) were condensed as before. The product crystallised in yellow needles from glacial acetic acid; m.p. 237°; yield, 14 g. (Found: N, 4.0. $C_{20}H_{19}O_7N$ requires N, 3.64 per cent.).

Reduction of the above Compound: Formation of Tetramethoxyindenoquinoline.—Nitrodimethoxybenzylidenedimethoxyhydrindone was reduced by zinc dust and acetic acid in the usual manner. The quinoline separated as an oily mass after the usual treatment, was dissolved in alcohol and converted into the hydrochloride. This crystallises in yellow needles on dilution, shrinking at 234° and melting with decomposition at 235°. (Found: N, 3.99. $C_{20}H_{19}O_4N$, HCl requires N, 3.75 per cent.).

